

MARCH/APRIL 1996
NO. 179

Piano

& KIMPHAM & BROADWAY

ANNUAL SUMMER STUDY GUIDE

STILL WILD AFTER ALL THESE YEARS: EARL WILD AT 80

26300
State Univ. North Texas
Library
Box 5188 Nt Station
Denton TX 76203-0188
JANUARY/FEBRUARY 97

Kimpham & Broadway Two Pianos, Four Hands, One Sound

DOES THE PIANO HAVE A FUTURE?
KEEPING YOUNG PERFORMERS HEALTHY

\$4.95 U.S./\$5.95 CANADA
0 74470 84331 3

MAR 11 1996
NON-CIRCULATING
U OF NT LIBRARIES

C O N T R I B U T O R S

Gustav Alink writes from The Netherlands. He has conducted extensive research on piano competitions and is an authority on the subject. His four books have gained wide recognition, and his fifth book will appear in 1997.

James Bonn, professor of music at the University of Southern California, tours and records with the Los Angeles Piano Quartet. His expertise with historical and modern keyboards has resulted in 16 recordings and extensive concert appearances throughout the world.

Nancy Bricard is professor of music at the University of Southern California and former chair of its department of keyboard studies. She is an authority on French pianism and has edited the major works of Ravel. She writes frequently on performance anxiety.

Jeffrey Chappell has played recitals and chamber music and appeared as concerto soloist throughout the United States and in Europe, Asia, and Latin America. He is on the faculties of Goucher College in Baltimore and the Levine School of Music in Washington, D.C.

Bradford Gowen is a concert pianist and member of the piano faculty at the University of Maryland in College Park. He performs as part of a piano duo with his wife, Maribeth.

Donald Manildi, a pianist and former broadcaster, is the curator of the International Piano Archives at the University of Maryland and a contributor to *American Record Guide*.

Virginia Marks is distinguished teaching professor and coordinator of keyboard studies at Bowling Green State University in Ohio. Her students have been frequent winners in local, state, and national competitions.

Victoria McArthur is program director of the piano pedagogy programs at Florida State University. An expert in cognitive psychology and motor learning, she lectures and publishes on the subjects of sight-reading, practice, and movement patterns.

Bryan Pezzone enjoys a career as a multistylistic pianist, composer, and improviser. He currently heads the keyboard department at the California Institute of the Arts. He has recorded a number of original artist disks for the Yamaha disklavier, premiered many works of contemporary music, and is actively involved in the studio scene. He divides his time between concerts and commercial work.

Scott McBride Smith is Executive Director of the Young Musicians Artists Association and associate editor of *Keyboard Companion*. He is a well-known clinician and private teacher in Southern California.

Sherwyn Woods, M.D., Ph.D. is Professor of Psychiatry and the Behavioral Sciences at the University of Southern California School of Medicine. He is the author of numerous publications in the field of psychiatry, including the interface between the dynamic and behavioral therapies. For many years he was the series editor for *Critical Issues in Psychiatry*.

Piano

& KEYBOARD

Marianne Uszler, *Editor*
Deidre Dolce, *Editorial Assistant*
Nancy Terzian, *Design*

Editorial Board

Jean Barr, Malcolm Bilson, Alan
Feinberg, Margo Garrett, Maurice
Hinson, Robert Levin, Ursula Oppens,
Jerome Rose, Robert Taub, Billy Taylor

Contributing Editors

Gail Berenson, Shelton Berg, Sarah
Cahill, Jeffrey Chappell, Larry Fine,
Bradford Gowen, James Keller,
Wilma Machover, Victoria McArthur,
Marilyn Neeley, Bryan Pezzone, John
Salmon, Scott McBride Smith,
Charles Timbrell

James Keough, *Publisher*
Julie Ghezzi, *Advertising*

PIANO & KEYBOARD
(ISSN 0031-9554) is published
bimonthly in January, March, May, July,
September, and November by
SparrowHawk Press, 223 San Anselmo
Avenue #3, San Anselmo, CA 94960.
Second-class postage paid at San
Anselmo, CA, and additional mailing
offices. Printed in USA.

POSTMASTER: Please send address
changes to PIANO & KEYBOARD, PO
Box 2626, San Anselmo, CA 94979-2626.

A single issue costs \$4.95; an individual
subscription is \$23.95 per year;
institutional subscriptions are \$36.00
per year. Foreign subscribers must order
air-mail delivery. Add \$7.50 per year for
Canada/Pan Am; \$15.00 elsewhere,
payable in local funds drawn on U.S.
bank. Please address all editorial
correspondence and inquiries
concerning advertising, subscriptions,
and retail sales to PIANO & KEYBOARD,
PO Box 2626, San Anselmo, CA 94979-
2626. Telephone (415) 458-8672, Fax
(415) 458-2955. All contents © 1996 by
SparrowHawk Press, Inc., James
Keough, Publisher.

The Bright Side

By Bryan Pezzone

We are so fortunate to be pianists. A few years ago it surprised me when one of my studio colleagues reiterated what seemed to be a well-known fact—"It's 'hard' for pianists and flutists." By hard, he meant hard to find work. I already knew that about flutists, since my wife is an exceptional flutist along with many others that we know who, a few times a year, show up at an orchestra audition along with 100 others. I hadn't imagined that the perception of pianists' opportunities was similar. Of course, we

all know the grim prospects of being an employed musician in a culture where worship of money, security, and self-gratification makes it less probable that the inverse ratio of the growing supply of musicians (especially pianists) and the shrinking demand for these musicians will change course soon. (Not to mention shrinking government funds and growing conservative attitudes toward the arts.)

Still, we are fortunate to be pianists—keyboardists, harpsichordists, organists, synth players, and teachers. And for many more reasons than the obvious, that being

musical self-sufficiency. What other instrumentalist (besides possibly the guitarist) has the ability to engage in a complete and fulfilling musical experience? To learn and play any of the Beethoven sonatas, and play it well, offers one of the most enviable experiences a person could have. Making allowances for different repertoire, this is true as well for the jazz pianist, the organist in church services, the synth gurus—in short, the soloist.

The solo keyboard experience is arguably unrivaled in its potential to provide the artist an opportunity to achieve the greatest heights of musical control and expression. It allows the individual to strive for and achieve a tremendous level of accomplishment. It drives us to be our best. The public has perennially adored the great soloist, from legendary accounts of Mozart and Clementi dueling in competition, through superstars such as Liszt, and into this century's giants—Rachmaninoff, Horowitz, Brendel, Cliburn, Rubinstein, and Pogorelich. And, with the regularly occurring international piano competitions providing a gateway to stardom, it is no wonder that anybody who treasures the fulfillment of mastering solo repertoire would want to ascend to the highest realm of visibility in order to share that experience and collect the accolades along the way.

The spotlight of pianistic stardom must be an incredible place. It is undoubtedly a place of great honor and represents a pinnacle of human achievement. We have all admired the abilities and stature of the great pianists, past and present. At some point, most of us (probably in our youth) have held close a belief that this life would be our destiny. And like many other young people who look to the Michael Jordans and Gary Kasparovs of the world for inspiration, we have looked to our heroes with hope for ourselves. There will always be "great" pianists, and there will always be room for a select few. They will always be incredible. Very few of us will ever reach that pinnacle, and most of us have long ago exchanged this dream of greatness for other things.

It is precisely because of these "other" things that we are so fortunate to be pianists. It is because of these "other" things that pianists should be viewed as extremely valuable and employable musicians. It is because of these "other"

Mozart, J. S. Bach, and Liszt are wonderful role models. They were multifaceted musicians who were involved with their communities.

things that none of us should feel that we have taken a back seat to higher callings or have failed on some level. These “other” things are all familiar areas—chamber work, accompanying, teaching, vocal coaching, musical theater, church work, jazz, historical instruments, electronics ... the list could go on. There are university and conservatory programs of exceptional quality that offer degrees and courses of study dedicated to many of the above. There are internationally renowned music festivals designed specifically to attract pianists primarily interested in chamber music and accompanying. There are many movements afoot to broaden the scope of curricula to encourage pianists to develop wider ranges of skills that not only increase their marketability, but expand their understanding of music and possibilities for music-making.

Despite this, the best talent seems to gravitate to performance programs that emphasize solo repertoire and concerti over chamber music and accompanying. There is more scholarship money devoted to these programs, and involvement in a conservatory or college as a “performance” major carries more status. Entrance requirements to most piano programs still reflect the same repertoire

stipulated for most piano competitions. As a result, the bulk of pianists’ energies while they progress through conservatory and college programs is focused on learning the same body of work that most pianists play. Worse, there are cases where students are discouraged from becoming too involved in a broad range of musical activities for fear that their solo repertoire will suffer. We have all heard far too many piano students tell how they were scolded by their piano

teachers for being interested in things other than “serious” studies. Although significant strides have been made to cultivate broader pianism and musicianship, the market continues to be flooded with enthusiasts who pursue a relatively narrow career path. And the system seems to support the continuation of this trend.

I want to reiterate that many music programs and educators are striving to create new curricula that serve the needs of the multifaceted student and prepare them for a career path that potentially may yield different employment opportunities. Many of these programs are in their infancy, and exactly how they should be implemented is ambiguous. Creating new curricula is a wonderful beginning. But it is not enough.

Young musicians entering institutions may be intellectually attracted to the philosophy and objectives of these programs, but much of the musical groundwork has already been established in the local com-

munity. It is in the *precollege* years that a musician’s outlook is most substantially influenced. Choice generally determines focus. How a person chooses to focus attention becomes habitual. It is during the earlier years that these “focusing” habits determine attitude, musical values, and propensities for developing particular musical skills. These early influences include parents, teachers, music teachers, school music programs, church, radio, TV, peers and friends, music to which they are exposed, and musical experiences in which they engage themselves (or are permitted to engage).

When young people are attracted to music-making or are prompted to train for a music career, there are stated demands. There is also a range of musical needs that developing musicians naturally strive to fulfill either for themselves or for others. I propose that the nature of the needs that they meet determine to a large extent how they will function as musicians in their future environments. What are these musical needs? Which needs does the developing musician attend to on a regular basis, and why?

The needs can generally be classified into two groups. Group One needs are immediate and personal. Group Two needs relate to some future event, like a performance or lesson, and are usually imposed by someone else. I’d like to explore needs in both of these groups, and draw some conclusions about how experiences with each, or both, play major roles in shaping a musician’s personality, abilities, and subsequent career opportunities.

Artistic children are inquisitive by nature, and they often exhibit a strong need for self-expression. For the young musician, the piano or keyboard is arguably the best musical instrument to provide a comprehensive vehicle for discovery and expression. Improvisation is a musical experience that is at once expressive and connected to discovery. Discovery is the essence. Trying to play by ear songs that one has heard elsewhere is another. Beginning pianists should be encouraged to do both from the start. I cannot stress enough how strongly I feel about the value of improvisation. Improvisation is to music as speaking is to language; it is musical speech. It has grammar, syntax, and meaning. Improvisation was expected in the classical era and earlier. Pianists

were expected to improvise cadenzas, realize figured bass, and create compositions spontaneously for concerts and competitions. Organists have sustained this tradition, and improvisation is usually a required component of major organ competitions. Harpsichordists are also generally comfortable realizing figured bass. But for the classical pianist, improvisation has long ago fallen by the wayside.

Improvising music provides one with the experience of how it feels to make music in direct response to one's emotions. What better way to connect with the fundamental creative process of the composer? I contend that developing a feeling for this is essential for breathing life into interpretation. Improvising is also the best way to meld one's discovery of how music works (theory) with expressive physical movement. And, perhaps most importantly, the improvisational experience is

subjective and non-judgmental. Mistakes are not mistakes in the traditional sense; mistakes are not something to feel bad

about. Mistakes can be more accurately described as unanticipated events. These unanticipated events can be used for many things. They can be springboards for further development. Understanding why these events may not fit the current context helps one achieve a deeper understanding of the language.

There are many ways that improvisation can be encouraged. A very simple thing is to help students play music that they already "hear" (such as songs and nursery rhymes). It is not necessary to play both hands at once. Next, have them make up music of their own. Put emphasis on the ideas of "beginning" and "ending" a phrase. Using scale notes is enough, but teaching chords much earlier is also a plus. One can suggest moods for improvisation. Children understand sad, happy, bored, and angry, and they can have fun exploring these moods musically. There are so many ways a developing musician can enjoy and explore improvisation; it's just a matter of being willing, and devoting time to it. I suggest that improvising should be a primary mode of music-making for young pianists. In this way, the relationship that develops between pianist

and piano becomes more personalized and filled with anticipation at every single encounter.

But what happens most of the time for the majority of beginning piano students? Our system of education is designed to dispense knowledge progressively, and then test that knowledge on a regular basis. Young people feel compelled to measure up, and quickly develop an opinion of their worth according to the grades they get and how often they are rewarded for the right answer. Piano lessons are often another periodic evaluation of right and wrong. It is a weekly evaluation of the student's preparation. Practicing can quickly become an experience associated with pressure and anxiety. Worry about how a lesson is going to "go" can begin to infect each moment of practicing. In order to relieve this anxiety, students begin to practice material

Making music with many musicians is the single most valuable education that musicians can have.

over and over again until they are assured that they can reproduce passage work with reliability. One can see the picture that begins to develop and continues to grow. The experience of playing the piano becomes less about music-making and more about avoiding criticism. Without question, regular practice and regular lessons are necessary in order to develop skill. But skill does not need to be born of anxiety. In fact, more profound levels of skill can be achieved if they are fueled by inspiration rather than fear. Cultivating a love of improvisation is one of the surest ways to sustain inspiration. Most classical musicians do not improvise (and even fear improvisation). Conversely, most self-taught musicians are primarily improvisers. Improvisation is basically subjective. The classically trained musician experiences deep anxiety not knowing if a choice is "right" or "wrong." Many self-taught musicians, on the other hand, disdain rigorous technical training fearing that this education may taint or even squelch their originality. Ideally, the best case scenario is one in which the cultivation of improvisation blends with traditional skills and tech-

niques. In this way, learning and performing music—any music—becomes not so much a problem to be solved and evaluated, but a living process of expression and discovery.

Another important area that needs to be addressed is how a pianist responds to the needs of other musicians in the immediate community. Making music in groups is arguably the fundamental musical experience. Evidence of this dates back to antiquity where music and dance (this is still true in many cultures) are inextricably related to ritual and social events. How many young classical pianists play music with other musicians? How many young pianists are enthusiastically involved in accompanying? Unless they are involved in junior or senior high school music programs, most young pianists live an isolated musical life. As a result (compared to other musicians), pianists usually have the

least ensemble experience prior to college. I recommend that every pianist learn a band or orchestral instrument in order to participate in the

ensemble programs available in schools. If not, then sing in a choir. Many young musicians also play in rock and roll or jazz bands. It is very natural for musical young people to do this, and is almost always entered into as play rather than assignment. Playing in bands is mostly about integrating into a "whole," with the exception of the "solo." Young people in bands learn how to listen to each other at least as much as (or more) than themselves. Band musicians develop a keen sense of rhythm and pulse. All these qualities are essential to good chamber music-making, but they are sorely lacking in first-year university keyboard students.

There are many community opportunities for the young pianist to engage himself in musical experiences with others. Every other musician who is not a pianist generally needs a pianist at some time to make music happen—classical or popular. A young pianist should be encouraged to respond affirmatively to the needs of other musicians in the immediate environment, regardless of style. The optimal situation is where a young musician participates in both pop and classical music, and in large and small

CHESKY RECORDS

“CHESKY SONICS—
AS LEGENDARY AS THE
MUSICIANS THEMSELVES.”

CD REVIEW

THE AHN TRIO
GINA BACHAUER
SIR JOHN BARBIROLLI
SIR ADRIAN BOULT
ANTAL DORATI
ANATOLE FISTOULARI
JOSEPH FLUMMERFELT
MALCOLM FRAGER
MASSIMO FRECCIA
NICOLA FRISARDI
CHARLES GERHARDT
ALEXANDER GIBSON
JASCHA HORENSTEIN
IGOR KIPNIS
JOSEF KRIPS
RENÉ LEIBOWITZ
BENITA MESHULAM
CHARLES MUNCH
ITZHAK PERLMAN
ASTOR PIAZZOLLA
GEORGE PRÉTRE
SIR MALCOLM SARGENT
GARY SCHOCKER
CHRISTOPH VON DOHNANYI
ALFRED WALLENSTEIN
EARL WILD
RANSOM WILSON

CONNECTICUT EARLY MUSIC FESTIVAL
LONDON SYMPHONY
MOZARTEUM ORCHESTER SALZBURG
NATIONAL PHILHARMONIC
NEW SYMPHONY
ORCHESTRA OF LONDON
ORQUESTA NOVA
ROYAL PHILHARMONIC
SOLISTI NEW YORK
SYMPHONIQUE DE PARIS
VIENNA STATE OPERA
WESTMINSTER CHOIR

CHESKY RECORDS
RADIO CITY STATION, P.O. BOX 1268
NEW YORK, NY 10101
1-800-331-1437 OR 212-586-7537
CHESKY ON-LINE: [HTTP://WWW.CHESKY.COM/MUSIC](http://www.chesky.com/music)

groups. In this way, the young musician develops ensemble skills, rhythmic skills, reading skills, and a working knowledge of diverse styles—not to mention occupying a position of great usefulness.

Very different pictures of developing musicians emerge depending on whether or not they respond to immediate needs. Many times students feel that they do not have time to engage in pursuing personal musical needs (improvising) or the needs of the musical community because they feel that they will not be as prepared for the evaluation (lesson, competition, or whatever). Each time they avoid the immediate need, or are discouraged from doing so, they miss an opportunity for growth. They exchange it for performance “insurance.”

I believe that in today’s music marketplace, opportunities for pianists to sustain a career are for those whose skills have developed as a result of meeting creative needs and the immediate needs of the community. I strongly encourage any teacher working with young people never to scold them for being interested in what I have earlier called “other” things. These “other” things should be the foundation of musicianship as it was centuries ago before the advent of the great piano soloists. Students who evolve this way usually take much more advantage of their musical environments. They are attracted to becoming involved in many things and continue to develop skill and insight as they respond to the needs of the magnificent pool of talent in our music schools. Making music with many musicians (along with continuous guidance of professors and professional musicians) is the single most valuable education that musicians can have. Their education is formed by the attitudes, activities, and available talent that surrounds them. For these students, traditional curricula often get in the way and impede them from doing as much as they could or would like to do. It is because of such students that curricula must be adjusted. But what needs to accompany curricular change at the advanced stages of education is change in how young musicians are prepared and encouraged. In this way, the good ideas behind these curricula can be made meaningful as they are populated by more enthusiastic and talented pianists ready to take advantage of

available opportunities. Career aspirations will be based more on meeting the needs students have always met before they entered the professional school as they will meet when they leave, degree in hand, and enter the general music marketplace.

From my perspective as an employed performer and teacher, there seems to be a continuous need for this type of musician. Many keyboardists and pianists I know enjoy stimulating and lucrative lives principally because of their skillful diversity. There comes a point where involvement in diverse areas begins to reinforce each area. Skill in classical techniques can bring more subtlety to popular languages; conversely, improvisational ability or expertise with electronics and MIDI can bring new life and insight to traditional repertoire, as well as expanding one’s ideas of technique and touch at the piano. I am convinced that, as applied to this profession, the old warning—do not become a jack-of-all-trades yet master of none—is irrelevant. It is a slogan that reinforces inhibition and contributes to the continuation of various musical prejudices—as well as limited employment opportunities. This idea needs to be discarded. It is a limiting concept. We are more capable than ever of meeting this challenge—as many already have. Through the media, we are so saturated with musical information and stylistic variety, that it is very natural for young musicians to develop affinities for, and skills in, diverse areas. It is also possible to develop these skills much more quickly than previously thought—especially if developed earlier in life.

As we move into the 21st century, the employed musician will be—more than ever—the skillfully diversified musician. If our systems of music education (from the local teacher to the most advanced professional schools) are to retain their viability through the next century, it will be because they will have readjusted their focus to foster a much broader concept of musicianship. This new foundation must include improvisation, emphasis on ensemble performance, and—for pianists—experience with all kinds of keyboards and pianos.

It is a time of transition. There are exciting challenges. Indeed, we are very fortunate to be pianists. ✚